

AN EFFICIENT AND EXTREME LEARNING MACHINE FOR AUTOMATED DIAGNOSIS OF BRAIN TUMOR

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ABSTRACT

An efficient automated system is needed to detect the tumor affected and non-affected region of human brain. Though there are traditional models which are already available for the said purpose, But they are facing the problem of excessive segmentation, greater time consumption, and high error rate and over fitting problem. The suggested method with the aid of preprocessing procedures enhances the contrast and quality of the input MRI images. From the pre-processed images, both texture and statistical characteristics are taken out for the subsequent classification process. Further with the aid of the Rapid Sine Cosine Swarm Optimisation method, dimensionality reduction has been accomplished. This has lowered training times and improved model accuracy. To precisely classify healthy and non-healthy images extreme learning algorithm is employed. Finally, to locate the exact tumor affected part of the image auto encoder-based segmentation is used. The proposed model is executed on the BRATS dataset and assessed utilizing a range of performance metrics, including accuracy, recall, F1-score, and precision, which yielded results of 98.93%, 99.21%, 97.67%, and 96.17% respectively, based on the training dataset.

Keywords: *Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Preprocessing, Rapid Sine Cosine Swarm Optimization, Dimensionality Reduction, Auto-Encoder*

1. INTRODUCTION

According to a recent World Health Organisation (WHO) statistical report, brain tumor is one of the main causes for cancer-related deaths worldwide [1]. Early brain tumour detection can help with timely treatment and prevent death, though this is not always possible. The most dangerous primary brain tumours in the central nervous system are called gliomas [2]. To find the tumour, the radiologist uses a variety of medical imaging techniques. Because of its safety, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) [3] is the technique of choice for treating brain tumours among the available techniques. Brain tumours are manually identified by the radiologist as part of routine practice. Tumour categorization is a non-automatic process that relies on the knowledge and

proficiency of the radiologists. The quantity of data that has to be regularly processed increases with the number of patients, which raises the expense and unreliability of readings that are only based on visual interpretation. Furthermore, the pathological classification of brain tumours poses more challenges than binary classification. Some of the factors that contribute to the related problems include the significant variation in size, intensity and shape for the same tumour type [4] and the comparable appearances for various disease types. A misdiagnosed brain tumour [5] can have disastrous effects and lower the patient's chances of survival. Creating computerized systems for image processing is becoming more and more common as a means of getting around the drawbacks of manual diagnosis. Conventional methods are unable to handle the

significant increase in data volume in the medical field. Storing and decoding the large medical data is one of the ongoing challenges in medical image analysis.

The Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD) system, which is capable of classifying certain tumors in brain MRI images, has been improved in a number of ways by numerous academics. Traditional machine learning techniques for classification often involve preprocessing, feature extraction, segmentation, feature selection, and classification. The successful operation of a CAD system [6] depends on feature extraction. The task is difficult and necessitates prior knowledge of the domain matter because the successful acquisition of important features is what determines how accurately the problem is classified. Contextual and hybrid features, wavelet and frequency features,

and spatial domain features are the various feature extraction model types that are used to classify the tumour class. To obtain an accurate diagnosis and prevent medical procedure and subjectivity, a practical diagnostics tool [7] for tumour classification and segmentation from MRI images must be developed. The advent of new technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning has had a significant impact on the medical industry [8]. These technologies have given medical departments including medical imaging the support tools they need.

Many algorithms based on machine learning are used in the segmentation and classification processes to interpret the MRI images and assist the radiologist in making a decision. [9]. The supervised method of brain tumor classification has a lot of promise, but in order to get the best features and feature selection methods, it needs specific training. Researchers have recently become interested in unsupervised techniques due to their automatic creation of features that reduce error rate, in addition to their excellent results. Deep Learning (DL)-based models have become increasingly important in medical image analysis, particularly for reconstruction, segmentation, and classification, thanks to recent developments [10]. However, the conventional works' drawbacks include excessive segmentation, over-fitting, high classification error, and high time consumption [11]. Thus, the purpose of this research project is to present a framework with high computational efficiency and competence for brain tumor recognition.

The work flow of the suggested method is:

- By eliminating the noisy pixels and boosting segmentation accuracy, an iterative thresholding based preprocessing methodology is used to enhance the quality and contrast of the input brain MRI.
- Texture features are taken from the preprocessed image to facilitate classification.
- The RSCSO technique is used during training to reduce the dimensionality and thereby improve the system performance.
- To precisely predict both normal and abnormal MRI results, ELM is employed.
- A segmentation mechanism based on Auto Encoder is utilised to extract the impacted area from the anomalous MRI pictures.

The remaining sections of the document are arranged as follows: Section 2 discusses techniques for brain tumour classification. In section 3, which outlines the general strategy for brain tumour detection, this paper presents a suggested method based on the problems that conventional techniques are facing. The comprehensive analysis of the results of the recommended methodology presented in Section 4. Section 5 discusses the overall synopsis of the entire work, including the conclusion, implications, and future work.

2. RELATED WORKS

The literature survey of conventional image processing technique used to create computerized framework for brain tumour identification is presented in this section. Additionally, it examines the works' advantages and drawbacks in light of their effectiveness in classification and detection.

The below section deals with the various methodologies applied in predictive and analytical models, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. Ensemble classification reduces error rates and enhances prediction accuracy; however, it is criticized for being less comprehensible and highly resource-intensive in terms of time and space [12]. A model combining Support Vector Machine (SVM) with Kalman Filter is effective in three-dimensional tasks and memory-efficient, yet it suffers from high training times, overlapping results, and unsuitability for large datasets [13]. The Random Forest paired with GLCM exhibits high robustness and mitigates overfitting but demands substantial computational power and has slow processing speeds [14]. Wavelet Transformation integrated with Decision Tree handles both discrete and continuous data without requiring slicing, but its

predictive ability is limited and prone to overfitting [15]. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) combined with Otsu Segmentation achieves better accuracy through weight sharing but struggles with high computational complexity and uneven illumination [16]. Lastly, CNN coupled with Thresholding offers fast processing, simplicity, and ease of deployment, though it faces challenges in threshold estimation and reduced performance in noisy conditions [17].

This review of literature indicates that creating a straightforward and computationally effective framework for medical image diagnosis is crucial for prediction and detection of brain tumours. As such, proposed work encourages the development of a novel and effective imaging method for building a framework for brain tumour diagnosis.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section offers a thorough explanation of the suggested system for diagnosing brain tumours with a proper workflow. This paper's original contribution is the creation of an automated framework for computationally efficient brain tumour identification from MRIs. In this paper, efficient image processing techniques are developed for this purpose. Here, system implementation and testing have been conducted using multiple MRI brain image datasets. Prior to classification, the unprocessed data to enhance contrast and image quality, MRI data is first pre-processed using an iterative thresholding technique. After that, the pre-processed image's statistical and texture features are taken out in order to precisely identify the tumor-affected area. Thus, the technique known as Rapid Sine Cosine Swarm Optimisation (RSCSO) is employed which also helps in reducing the classifier training time by reducing the dimensionality of the feature set. Using the best features, ELM is used to distinguish between images without tumours and those with tumours. If the identified MRIs are tumor-affected, the tumour section is cropped with the help of an auto-encoder based segmentation technique. Proposed RSCSO-ELM system's main advantages include reduced over segmentation, minimal processing time, high accuracy, and less overfitting.

The workflow of the suggested work is shown with the help of figure 1, where the raw input MRI is first pre-processed using an iterative thresholding technique. After that, the pre-processed image's statistical and texture features are extracted. The technique known as Rapid Sine Cosine Swarm Optimisation is used to reduce the dimensionality of

feature set so as to reduce the classifier training time. Using the best features, an Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) algorithm is employed to distinguish between images without tumours and those with tumours.

The main reason of choosing RSCSO-ELM technique is to increase the accuracy and prediction performance of the classification system with simplified computational operations. By using the RSCSO algorithm, the dimensionality of features is reduced in the proposed model, which supports to increase the speed of classifier with low time and high accuracy. In addition to that, the number of features fed to the classifier for training and testing is greatly optimized with the use of this optimization algorithm. Then, the ELM mechanism is specifically used to identify the presence of tumor with its accurate location according to the input features. When compared to the other tumor detection models, the combination of proposed RSCSO-ELM provides a highly accurate prediction results. Thus, we have used an integrated RSCSO-ELM technique in the proposed work for brain tumor detection. When compared to the other classification methods, the suggested RSCSO-ELM offers a higher accuracy.

Fig 1. Proposed Methodology

A. Preprocessing technique

There are several different image modalities, including CT, MRI, and X-rays. MRI is a useful imaging method for detecting brain tumours because it is completely safe and produces crisp, high-contrast images, unlike X-ray and CT scans. Brain MRI typically uses T1- and T2-weighted sequences. T2-weighted brain MRI can be used to diagnose brain cancers because abnormal lesions show up as brighter than the surrounding normal tissues[18]. For this reason, T2-weighted brain sequences are commonly utilised as a data set for brain tumour diagnosis. This system removes background using the adaptive threshold method. The iterative procedure for enhancing contrast and image quality.

The steps below provide a clear explanation of how input images are pre-processed.

First, the image's minimum BI_{mn} and maximum BI_{mx} values are used to determine the initial threshold, as illustrated below:

$$Th_s = \frac{BI_{mx} + BI_{mn}}{2} \tag{1}$$

The image is divided into two sections as shown below, based on the estimated threshold:

$$\begin{aligned} P1 &= \{BI(i, j) | BI(i, j) > Th_s\} \\ P2 &= \{BI(x, y) | BI(x, y) \leq Th_s\} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Next, to ascertain the shifts in thresholds, grey averages in each subpart, such as $P1_m$ and $P2_m$, are estimated, as shown below:

$$Th_s = \frac{P1_m + P2_m}{2} \tag{3}$$

Where the mean values of the two subparts are denoted by $P1_m$ and $P2_m$

To eliminate the noise and to improve the contrast after background removal the non local mean filtering method is used in this work. The below equation gives the details about how to calculate Gaussian Weighted average value

$$O(i, j) = \sum_{j \in BI} \omega(i, j) \times BI(i) \tag{4}$$

$$\delta(i, j) = \frac{e^{-\frac{\|\omega(y_i) - \omega(y_j)\|_2^2}{a^2}}}{Normalized\ factor} \tag{5}$$

$$Normalized\ factor = \sum_j F_j \tag{6}$$

$$F_j = e^{-\frac{\|\omega(y_i) - \omega(y_j)\|_2^2}{a^2}} \tag{7}$$

Moreover, the brain image's contrast is markedly improved by the use of histogram equalisation. The sub-images' mean and standard deviation are estimated during this process. A tumor's brightness and magnetic resonance imaging features are similar to those of a skull, suggesting that the skull may have some impact on image classification. Since the tumour is limited to the brain's exterior, the location information can be used to remove the skull, which will lessen its impact on tumour classification. Therefore, the goal of skull removal is to improve segmentation accuracy and efficiency. Preprocessing also reduces the risk of incorrect classification rates and excessive segmentation of images.

B) Optimization using Rapid Sine Cosine Swarm Technique

The goal of feature extraction is to precisely identify the tumor's location within the provided MRI image. Sine-cosine optimisation is a population-based algorithm that is commonly employed to solve intricate problems. It has the same primary operations of exploration and exploitation as the other stochastic algorithms. In this model, different regions of the searching space are investigated by means of the sine-cosine functions. Then, by choosing the most pertinent and ideal features, the RSCSO algorithm is used to reduce the dimensionality of the features. The RSCSO algorithm is used in this detection framework because of its higher convergence rate and lower computational complexity.

The parameter of learning is updated with the new velocity and position models in this case, which can be seen below

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i(k + 1) &= \delta \times \alpha_i(k) + L_p t_1 (G_i^{best} - c_i(k)) + \\ &G_p t_2 (G_i^{best} - c_i(k)) \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$c_i(k + 1) = c_i(k) + \alpha_i(k + 1) \tag{9}$$

Where, α_i represents position
 k – Particle numbers
 δ -- Coefficient of inertia
 L_p --weight coefficient of local position
 G_p --weight coefficient of global position
 t_1, t_2 -- random numbers

C_i -- Position
 G_i^{best} Current best solution

The position equation is represented as follows:

$$C_i^{k+1} = \begin{cases} C_i^k + r_1 \times \sin(r_2) \times |r_3 G^{best} - C_i^k|, & r_4 < 0.5 \\ C_i^k + r_1 \times \cos(r_2) \times |r_3 G^{best} - C_i^k|, & r_4 \geq 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where, C_i^{k+1} --- updated position
 $r_1, r_2, r_3,$ and r_4 --- random numbers

The output of this algorithm is the best optimal solution, which is determined based on this process. The obtained solution can then be used to select the pertinent features for the classifier training and testing procedures.

Fig 2 (A). Input (B). Ground Truth, (C). Binary Region, (D). Clustered Region, (E). Segmented Portions

C) Classification using Extreme Learning Machine

After selecting features, the supplied MRI brain image is classified via the ELM classification approach as either normal or affected by a tumour. Since the ELM is one of the advanced or recent supervised machine learning algorithms, specifically suited for complex classification and regression problems. In this technique, the hidden layer's weights and biases are chosen at random, and the output weights are analytically determined by an uncomplicated mathematical operation. Hence, it requires a little computational effort to train new classifiers. Moreover, researchers' interest in ELM has grown steadily over the past few years, and numerous ELM versions have been proposed to

enhance the algorithm's performance. More specifically, this algorithm has been used to optimize several issues in the fields of pattern recognition, machine learning, artificial intelligence, and other related fields. Due to its outstanding performance, it is successfully applied in many medical imaging applications for resolving the real time problems. This is a feed forward neural network with one hidden layer, where input weights are chosen at random and output weights are determined analytically. This kind of learning model effectively improves the generalization performance of classification with increased learning speed. Therefore, the proposed work intends to apply an ELM based classification algorithm for identifying the presence of tumor from brain MRIs.

This model considers training samples $\{(H_i, tar_j)\}_{j=1}^N$ where g hidden nodes, x classes and N samples are included, with an activation function of $\rho(h)$. This is shown as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^g \omega_i \rho_i(h_j) = \sum_{i=1}^g \omega_i \rho(\tau_i \times h_j + \beta_i) = OP_j \quad (11)$$

Where, $j = 1, 2 \dots N,$

$$h_j = [h_{j1}, h_{j2}, h_{j3} \dots h_{jn}]^S$$

$$tar_j = [tar_{j1}, tar_{j2} \dots tar_{jn}]^S$$

$$\tau_i = [\tau_{i1}, \tau_{i2} \dots \tau_{in}]^S \text{ as weight value}$$

$$\beta_i \text{ Indicates the bias value}$$

$$OP_j \text{ Represents the output value}$$

Additionally, ELM is used in conjunction with one against all coding to transmit multiple discriminations to different regression output functions. It first computes the actual sample of each output before utilising the actual output index to assign anticipated labels. The best solution is found using the regularised least-squares method when the pseudo-inverse is statistically unstable. Next, in order to predict the classified label, the identity matrix is calculated using the regularisation parameter. This mechanism's primary advantages are its quick training speed, low time requirement, high classification accuracy, and ease of implementation.

D) Segmentation – Auto Encoder

Precise tumour segmentation is a critical step in computerized brain tumour recognition and surgical planning. Thus, the next stage is segmentation to precisely extract the affected brain region after we obtain the predicted image that shows a tumour. Here, the auto-encoder segmentation mechanism is

used to accurately segment brain tumours in a shorter amount of time. It has three different layers such as input, output and the hidden layers. The goal of each layer's training is to lower the reconstruction's cross-entropy. By training the first layer, this segmentation technique primarily reduces the average reconstruction error. The input, ground truth, binary area, clustered region, and segmented sections of the brain MRI image are shown in Fig. 2.

4. RESULTS

Using a variety of datasets and assessment metrics, this section verifies and tests the outcomes of the suggested tumour detection method. The datasets used in this study are BRATS 2012 to 2018[19] , TCIA –MRI/CT scan[20]and Kaggle repository[21] etc.

In the proposed work, the different types of brain image datasets such as BRATS, TCIA and Kaggle are used to validate the tumor detection efficiency and performance of the RSCSO-ELM techniques. Moreover, these are all the widely used emerging public benchmarking datasets, each of which having unique image samples with different dimensions. To analyze the classification accuracy of ELM, these datasets are trained with the proposed system. Moreover, the superiority of the RSCSO-ELM is proved by comparing its performance with other recent approaches with the use of these datasets. Moreover, a variety of parameter types, including the following ones, are used to validate and compare the outcomes of the RSCSO-ELM approach.

Accuracy: It evaluates each and every correctly positioned pixel in an image and is calculated using the formula below:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TrPos+TrNeg}{TrPos+TrNeg+F_{Pos}+FaNeg} \quad (12)$$

Sensitivity: quantifies the percentage of true positives that are correctly identified. It is calculated using the subsequent formula:

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TrPos}{TrPos+FaNeg} \quad (13)$$

Specificity: determines the proportion of real negatives that are correctly detected. It is calculated in this way:

$$Specificity = \frac{TrNeg}{TrNeg+FaPos} \quad (14)$$

Positive Predictive Value: The true positive (TP) indicator shows the probability of accurately classified pixels:

$$PPV = \frac{TrPos}{TrPos+F_{Pos}} \quad (15)$$

F1-Score: The harmonic mean of recall and precision is used to compute the F1 score. A harmonic mean is a kind of average that is computed by multiplying the total number of values in a dataset by the reciprocal of each value in the dataset. The F1 score has a value between 0 and 1, where 1 represents a better result.

$$F1 - score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision+Rec} \quad (16)$$

Where, $TrPos$ ---true positives
 $TrNeg$ ---true negatives
 $FaPos$ ---false positives
 $FaNeg$ ---false negatives

The comparison of accuracy with respect to various classification techniques for brain tumor identification and classification is represented with the help of Fig 3. In this figure the accuracy of existing optimisation integrated machine learning/deep learning techniques are compared with the proposed RSCSO-ELM model. This comparison technique can recognize the tumour with better accuracy.

Fig 3. Accuracy Of Various Classification Methods

Based on the various measures like accuracy, precision, sensitivity, fl-score, and specificity, Figure 4 shows the overall performance analysis of

the suggested and traditional methodologies [22]. The analysis of all the outcome parameters shows that, based on the results, the RSCSO and ELM mechanism has generated the best results in terms of all recommended parameters.

Fig 4. Comparative evaluation

The time taken for segmentation and error rate of the suggested classification methods and the conventional [24] methods are compared in Fig. 5. The suggested method, RSCSO-ELM, took less time to segment and classifies the tumour when compared to other methods. The suggested classifier's error rate is effectively decreased as a result of the appropriate feature extraction and selection procedures. The suggested RSCSO integrated ELM outperforms the current classifiers with superior prediction outcomes, it is concluded based on the results. Here the error rate of existing classification algorithms and proposed optimization integrated ELM classification technique are compared. According to the results it is concluded that the suggested method outperformed the existing classifiers with better prediction results.

Fig 5. Time complexity and error rate

According to the outputs received, it is concluded that the proposed RSCSO integrated ELM outperformed the existing classifiers with better prediction results.

In the proposed brain tumor diagnosis system, an advanced image processing techniques are used to accurately identify the abnormal tissues in the brain region. Specifically, the RSCSO-ELM techniques play a vital role in the proposed system, since it helps to obtain improved performance outcomes. With the use of RSCSO, the dimensionality of the features is reduced, which supports to improve the training speed of the classifier with better accuracy. Moreover, this optimization algorithm simplifies the complex computational modelling of the tumor detection system. Moreover, the ELM technique can identify the abnormal tissues from the given brain image according to the reduced number of features selected. Therefore, the proposed technique outperforms the existing techniques with better performance results.

5. DISCUSSIONS

The deep convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is used by Ayadi, et al[23] for the detection and classification of MRI brain tumor. The Figshare dataset is used to train the recommended model in preparation for system testing and deployment. But the model requires a lot of time to train and test, which makes the system more complex. For automated brain tumour detection, Veeramuthu et al. [24] used a NN classification model based on deep learning. Here feature-based classification, image-based classification, and their hybridization has all been applied. A hybridised deep features-based

machine learning classification algorithm was developed by Kang et al. [25] for the purpose of detecting and classifying brain tumours. In this case, feature extraction and classification are carried out after the picture has been cropped and resized. The set of deep features is then extracted using the CNN model's dense net, inception, and res net layers. After that, the output result is predicted using a group of nine distinct machine learning algorithms. To further enhance the quality of the raw MRI brain image thresholding, outer contour extraction, edge point identification, and image cropping were also carried out. This model may have a major flaw in that it greatly increases the complexity of detection due to the inclusion of numerous techniques. For MRI brain tumour identification and classification, Raza et al. [26] employed a hybrid deep learning mechanism. The implementation and testing of this system make use

of the CE-MRI dataset. According to the analysis of this study, the CNN is a highly suitable system for detecting brain tumours. But the suggested model's performance is impacted by its increased computational complexity and time requirements.

A multi-scale CNN mechanism was used by Diaz-Pernas et al. [27] to create computerized system for the identification and segmentation of brain tumours. Here, the recommended diagnosis framework has been implemented and tested using the T1-CE MRI image dataset. Additionally, this system performs concatenation, classification, and scale feature extraction. Furthermore, the study employs 5-fold cross validation to evaluate the multi-scale CNN model's detection efficacy and competence. In particular, it offers the advantages of being simple to comprehend and having less overfitting.

Garg et al. [28] developed a hybrid ensemble learning classifier by fusing the methods of Random Forest (RF), Decision Tree (DT), and K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) in order to precisely diagnose brain tumours. Here, the Otsu thresholding mechanism is used to separate the foreground and background regions of the MRI input. The best features for identifying brain tumours are then extracted using a system made up of Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Grey Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) techniques. The scheme of majority voting is used to predict whether the tumour is benign or malignant. The primary flaw in this work is the increased level of accuracy that was necessary.

For the classification of brain tumours, Khairandish et al. [29] used a model made up of CNN-SVM hybrid model integrated with threshold-based segmentation technique. In this case, CNN is used to help with feature extraction, and SVM is used to make decisions. Additionally, image resizing, skull removal, and filtering are done during the first stage of input image preprocessing. The input is then divided into several segments using the thresholding-based segmentation algorithm, which aids in achieving a higher accuracy. Nevertheless, it faces issues with excessive segmentation, high feature dimensionality, and increased processing time. A systematic survey is done on the various machine learning approaches used for brain tumour identification and grading by Bucklak et al. [30]. It also goes over the various validation techniques that are employed to determine which method is best for detecting tumours.

An enhanced deep learning mechanism was proposed by Sadad et al. [31] to create a multi-classification model for MRI brain tumour detection. In this case, the freeze and fine-tune operations are used in conjunction with transfer learning to help extract a good number of features from input MRIs. The high-resolution images are produced using the contrast stretching algorithm during preprocessing. Additionally, the data augmentation mechanism reduces the amount of training data, which effectively minimizes the amount of time needed for training and testing operations. In order to create a brain tumor diagnosis system with limited training loss and maximum accuracy, Tiwari et al. [32] employed a CNN mechanism. A detailed review about the effects of medical image processing techniques on brain tumor detection is discussed in [33].

6. CONCLUSION

The classification of brain tumor is considered as the major area of research on medical science field. Numerous techniques have been proposed for the classification of various tumour types. These methods produced a satisfactory performance in terms of classification accuracy. Tumour classification is still a problem though, and needs to be properly addressed. Accurate categorization can be further increased with the aid of a strong framework. The suggested work aims to develop a classification framework for brain tumour with high classification accuracy and low complexity.

In the suggested work the quality of image is enhanced by using an iterative preprocessing algorithm. Then, the statistical and texture characteristics are taken out from the previously analysed input MRI to simplify the classifier's operations. Thus by using RSCSO dimensionality reduction process is performed by choosing the most important features based on global optimization solution. The classification of normal and abnormal MRI is done by using ELM mechanism followed by segmentation which is done by using the auto encoder algorithm. Various measures are used to validate and compare the performance and outcomes of the suggested RSCSOELM techniques during evaluation. The suggested RSCSOELM model, according to the estimated results, performs better than alternative algorithms with high performance prediction results. Within the medical sciences, one of the most significant areas of research is the classification of brain tumours. Numerous techniques have been proposed for the classification of various tumour types.

These methods produced a satisfactory performance in terms of classification accuracy. Tumour classification is still a problem though, and needs to be properly addressed. Accurate categorization can be further increased with the aid of a strong framework. Creating a brain tumour classification model with low complexity and high classification accuracy is the main objective of this research project. The proposed model uses an iterative preprocessing algorithm to first enhance the visual quality of the image. Next, in order to make the classifier's operations simpler, the texture and statistical features are taken out of the previously processed image. Thus, by selecting the most pertinent features based on the global optimal solution, the RSCSO mechanism is used to reduce the dimensionality of features.

The given MRI is then classified as normal or abnormal by using the ELM. If the predicted image is abnormal, the auto encoder segmentation technique is applied to accurately crop the tumour affected area with improved segmentation accuracy. Various measures are used to validate and compare the performance and outcomes of the suggested RSCSOELM techniques during evaluation. The suggested RSCSOELM model, according to the estimated results, performs better than alternative algorithms with high performance prediction results.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Gurunathan And B. Krishnan, "A Hybrid Cnn-Glm Classifier For Detection And Grade Classification Of Brain Tumor," *Brain Imaging And Behavior*, Vol. 16, Pp. 1410-1427, 2022.
- [2] G. U. Kaya And T. O. Onur, "A Comparative Study For Brain Tumor Detection Using Segmentation Based On Soft Computing And Thresholding Methods," *Journal Of Electrical Engineering, Electronics, Control And Computer Science*, Vol. 8, Pp. 21-32, 2021.
- [3] A. Ramesh Kumar And H. Kuttiappan, "Detection Of Brain Tumor Size Using Modified Deep Learning And Multilevel Thresholding Utilizing Modified Dragonfly Optimization Algorithm," *Concurrency And Computation: Practice And Experience*, Vol. 34, P. E7016, 2022.
- [4] N. Nagar, N. Pandey, And A. Agwekar, "Brain Tumour Detection And Classification Using Cnn," *International Journal Of Engineering And Applied Physics*, Vol. 2, Pp. 472-479, 2022.
- [5] S. Ayub, Kannan, S Shitharth, R. Jagadeesh, R. Alsini, T. Hasanin, Et Al., "Lstm-Based Rnn Framework To Remove Motion Artifacts In Dynamic Multicontrast Mr Images With Registration Model," *Wireless Communications And Mobile Computing*, Vol. 2022, 2022.
- [6] D. M. Toufiq, A. M. Sagheer, And H. Veisi, "Brain Tumor Segmentation From Magnetic Resonance Image Using Optimized Thresholded Difference Algorithm And Rough Set," 2022.
- [7] A. Jain, A. Malviya, D. Bajaj, R. Bhavsar, And A. Savyanavar, "Brain Tumor Detection Using Mlops And Hybrid Multi-Cloud," In *2022 Ieee International Conference On Blockchain And Distributed Systems Security (Icbds)*, 2022, Pp. 1-6.
- [8] T. A. Soomro, L. Zheng, A. J. Afifi, A. Ali, S. Soomro, M. Yin, Et Al., "Image Segmentation For Mr Brain Tumor Detection Using Machine Learning: A Review," *Ieee Reviews In Biomedical Engineering*, 2022.
- [9] N. Molachan, K. Manoj, And D. A. S. Dhas, "Brain Tumor Detection That Uses Cnn In Mri," In *2021 Asian Conference On Innovation In Technology (Asiancon)*, 2021, Pp. 1-7.
- [10] D. V. Gore, A. K. Sinha, And V. Deshpande, "Automatic Cad System For Brain Diseases Classification Using Cnn-Lstm Model," In *Emerging Technologies In Data Mining And*

- Information Security, Ed: Springer, 2023, Pp. 623-634.
- [11] S. Pandey, "Brain Tumor Detection Using Cnn," Turkish Journal Of Computer And Mathematics Education (Turcomat), Vol. 12, Pp. 4597-4603, 2021.
- [12] M. A. Alamir, "A Novel Acoustic Scene Classification Model Using The Late Fusion Of Convolutional Neural Networks And Different Ensemble Classifiers," Applied Acoustics, Vol. 175, P. 107829, 2021.
- [13] B. Chen, L. Zhang, H. Chen, K. Liang, And X. Chen, "A Novel Extended Kalman Filter With Support Vector Machine Based Method For The Automatic Diagnosis And Segmentation Of Brain Tumors," Computer Methods And Programs In Biomedicine, Vol. 200, P. 105797, 2021.
- [14] I. H. Rather, S. Minz, And S. Kumar, "Hybrid Texture-Based Feature Extraction Model For Brain Tumour Classification Using Machine Learning," In Emerging Technologies In Data Mining And Information Security, Ed: Springer, 2023, Pp. 445-455.
- [15] R. Garg And O. P. Sangwan, "Hybrid Classifier For Brain Tumor Detection And Classification," In Artificial Intelligence And Speech Technology, Ed: Crc Press, 2021, Pp. 239-245.
- [16] V. V. Kumar And P. G. K. Prince, "Magnitude Normalized And Otsu Intensity Based Brain Tumor Detection Using Magnetic Resonance Images," Iete Journal Of Research, Pp. 1-11, 2021.
- [17] R. Remya And K. Parimala Geetha, "A Novel Thresholding Approach To Find Out The Brain Tumor Region From Mr Images," Iete Journal Of Research, Pp. 1-9, 2021.
- [18] Pathan, S., & Balaji, D. S. (2022). A Detailed Analysis On Medical Image Processing Techniques Used For Brain Tumor Detection And Classification. Journal Of Theoretical And Applied Information Technology, 100(11).
- [19] (2020). Multimodal Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2020: Data Available: <https://www.Med.Upenn.Edu/Cbica/Brats2020/Data.Html>
- [20] "The Cancer Imaging Archive (Tcia)," 2022.
- [21] (2020). Open Access Series Of Imaging Studies (Oasis) Available: <https://www.Oasis-Brains.Org/>
- [22] (2016). The Internet Brain Segmentation Repository (Ibsr) Available: <https://www.Nitrc.Org/Projects/Ibsr>
- [23] (2020). Kaggle Dataset. Available: <https://www.Kaggle.Com/Datasets>
- [24] G. Garg And R. Garg, "Brain Tumor Detection And Classification Based On Hybrid Ensemble Classifier," Arxiv Preprint Arxiv:2101.00216, 2021.
- [25] M. Mudda, R. Manjunath, And N. Krishnamurthy, "Brain Tumor Classification Using Enhanced Statistical Texture Features," Iete Journal Of Research, Vol. 68, Pp. 3695-3706, 2022.
- [26] A. Dixit And A. Nanda, "An Improved Whale Optimization Algorithm-Based Radial Neural Network For Multi-Grade Brain Tumor Classification," The Visual Computer, Vol. 38, Pp. 3525-3540, 2022.
- [27] W. Ayadi, W. Elhamzi, I. Charfi, And M. Atri, "Deep Cnn For Brain Tumor Classification," Neural Processing Letters, Vol. 53, Pp. 671-700, 2021.
- [28] A. Veeramuthu, S. Meenakshi, G. Mathivanan, K. Kotecha, J. R. Saini, V. Vijayakumar, Et Al., "Mri Brain Tumor Image Classification Using A Combined Feature And Image-Based Classifier," Frontiers In Psychology, Vol. 13, 2022.
- [29] J. Kang, Z. Ullah, And J. Gwak, "Mri-Based Brain Tumor Classification Using Ensemble Of Deep Features And Machine Learning Classifiers," Sensors, Vol. 21, P. 2222, 2021.
- [30] A. Raza, H. Ayub, J. A. Khan, I. Ahmad, A. S. Salama, Y. I. Daradkeh, Et Al., "A Hybrid Deep Learning-Based Approach For Brain Tumor Classification," Electronics, Vol. 11, P. 1146, 2022.
- [31] F. J. Díaz-Pernas, M. Martínez-Zarzuela, M. Antón-Rodríguez, And D. González-Ortega, "A Deep Learning Approach For Brain Tumor Classification And Segmentation Using A Multiscale Convolutional Neural Network," In Healthcare, 2021, P. 153.
- [32] I. Abd El Kader, G. Xu, Z. Shuai, S. Saminu, I. Javaid, And I. Salim Ahmad, "Differential Deep Convolutional Neural Network Model For Brain Tumor Classification," Brain Sciences, Vol. 11, P. 352, 2021.
- [33] Pathan, S., & Balaji, D. S. (2022). A Detailed Analysis On Medical Image Processing Techniques Used For Brain Tumor Detection And Classification. Journal Of Theoretical And Applied Information Technology, 100(11).